

FORMING COMPLEX SHAPES FROM ALIGNED, DISCONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC SHEET MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Thermoformable sheet materials offer the opportunity to form a wide variety of complex shapes economically. A highly aligned, long fiber, drawable sheet structure is described. New analytical techniques are needed to aid in the forming of highly contoured parts. The ability to predict the location and extent of sheet thinning is critical to an optimum formed part. Analytical techniques are developed for several planar geometries. A novel modeling technique is described that was used to predict the thinning during the forming of a highly contoured seat part. Based on this technique, a variable thickness panel was analytically developed which allowed a seat of uniform thickness to be produced.

INTRODUCTION

Currently the fabrication of a complex three dimensional shape in thermoset composite materials is expensive. The entire structure must be hand laid up ply by ply with each ply consisting of multiple pieces carefully cut to conform to the part curvature. Thermoplastic composites offer the possibility of post-forming a prefabricated sheet structure. However, if continuous fibers are used in this structure, the formability is severely restricted due to the limitation on fiber stretching. A part with continuous fibers can be formed as long as the plies slip relative to each other¹ and the plies don't have to wrinkle to conform to the part geometry.² Short chopped fibers in a thermoplastic matrix solve these problems, but to the detriment of material properties. A balance is possible by using highly ordered, long discontinuous fibers in a thermoplastic matrix. Du Pont's ordered staple formable sheet materials are highly formable, yet retain 90% of the continuous fiber properties.³ This material has been used to fabricate a number of parts in a variety of sizes and shapes⁴ and the labor savings can be significant.⁵

A major concern in the fabrication of parts from thermoformable materials is the thinning of the sheet due to forming. If the material has continuous fibers, it will thin due to fiber spreading in the transverse fiber direction. If the material has discontinuous fibers, it will thin in all directions. Since it is easier to form a part with a drawable material, the ability to predict the location and degree of thinning becomes critical. Several techniques, both analytical and physical, will be reviewed for various geometries.

FORMING COMPLEX SHAPES

Forming complex, three dimensional parts from drawable composite materials requires a combination of analytical and experimental work. The analytical work is required for tooling design, preform design and part stress analysis. A complete understanding of the drawing of the material is needed since the area of greatest thinning is often the area of greatest stress. Once this analysis is done, the tooling must be built and forming trials begun. It is only then that a complete understanding of the part forming can be developed. The results of these trials can then be fed back to adjust the analytical models to converge on the optimum final part.⁶

The location and degree of thinning has implications for what tooling is selected. If matched metal molds are used for forming and reconsolidation, then the precise thickness over the entire surface of the part must be known to insure uniform part consolidation. Either the mold cavity must be adjusted for this thickness variation or the formable sheet must be contoured. The latter allows for easier optimization once the tooling is fabricated. An alternative is to use solid rubber or rubber-faced tools that would adjust to small variations in sheet thickness. The techniques developed here predict the location and degree of sheet thinning to permit contouring the initial sheet thickness so that the final part will have uniform thickness. This permits the use of matched metal tooling with a constant thickness gap.

FORMING MODELS

A macro modeling approach was developed that assumes the material is quasi-isotropic, uniform through the thickness and isothermal during forming. This approach is independent of the type of discontinuous fiber and resin system, as long as the melt viscosity is low enough and the forming times slow enough to permit thermoforming without breaking fibers.

1. Uniaxial Stretching (One Dimensional)

In the uniaxial stretching model, equal and opposite forces are applied to the ends of a sheet. The initial elements have a length in the longitudinal direction of L_0 , width in the transverse direction of W_0 and thickness of T_0 . The force applies a uniform tensile strain to this sheet. Because the material is clamped cold, the edges where the force is applied are assumed to evenly distribute this load. This strain field yields a final element with dimensions L_1 , W_1 and T_1 . Fig. 1 shows a section of this sheet a distance from the clamps.

Fig. 1 Diagram of uniaxial stretching of a flat panel.

The basic assumption for plastic deformation is the constancy of volume. For this uniaxial case, the transverse strain is assumed equal to the normal strain. Given this, the relationship between the initial thickness and the final thickness depends solely on the degree of strain applied. Because the elastic strains are small compared to the plastic strains, the applied strain is equal to the resulting deformation or draw.

Based on these assumptions, the constancy of volume may be expressed as:

$$L_0 W_0 T_0 = L_1 W_1 T_1$$

Or:
$$\frac{L_1 W_1 T_1}{L_0 W_0 T_0} = 1 \quad (1)$$

Engineering strains in the longitudinal, transverse and normal directions are defined as:

$$\epsilon_L = \frac{L_1 - L_0}{L_0} = \frac{L_1}{L_0} - 1 \quad \epsilon_T = \frac{W_1}{W_0} - 1 \quad \epsilon_N = \frac{T_1}{T_0} - 1 \quad (2)$$

Since $\epsilon_T = \epsilon_N$,
$$\frac{W_1}{W_0} = \frac{T_1}{T_0}$$

Substituting this into (1) and solving for the non-dimensional thickness ratio yields:

$$\frac{T_0}{T_1} = \sqrt{\frac{L_1}{L_0}} = \sqrt{1 + \epsilon_L} \quad (3)$$

Once the final thickness T_1 and the thickness per ply T_{PLY} is set this may be converted to

the actual number of plies:

$$N_{PLIES} = \frac{T_0}{T_{PLY}} \quad (4)$$

FIG. 2 Graph of thickness ratio as a function of longitudinal strain. Number of plies based on final thickness of 2.54 mm (0.100 in) with 0.127 mm (0.005 in) thick plies.

2. Biaxial Stretching (Two Dimensional)

In the biaxial stretching model, forces are applied that result in a uniform deformation in two perpendicular directions.

Fig. 3 Diagram of biaxial stretching of a flat panel.

Here the elongation is determined solely by the longitudinal and transverse strains applied. Therefore, equation (1) may be expressed as:

$$\frac{T_0}{T_1} = \frac{L_1 W_1}{L_0 W_0}$$

or in terms of the applied engineering strains:

$$\frac{T_0}{T_1} = [(1 + \epsilon_L)(1 + \epsilon_T)] \quad (7)$$

From equation (4) the actual number of plies are calculated.

Fig. 4. Graph of thickness ratio as a function of longitudinal and transverse strains. No. of plies based on final thickness of 2.54 mm (0.1 in) with 0.127 mm (0.005 in) plies.

3. Planar Bending (Two Dimensional)

If a pure bending moment is induced in a flat panel and it is plastically deformed, then it will thin toward the outer radius. The degree of thinning will depend on the part geometry and is critical to the parts structural properties. To simplify this geometry, the formed inside radius of curvature (R_0) is made constant and assumed to be the neutral axis. This is realistic since any compression on the panel would buckle the fibers and decrease the final part properties.

Fig. 5 Diagram of planar bending of a flat panel.

The polar engineering strains are:

$$\epsilon_z = \frac{(T_y - T_0)}{T_0} \quad \epsilon_R = \frac{(W_y - W_0)}{W_0} \quad \epsilon_\theta = \frac{(R_y - R_0)}{R_0} \quad (8)$$

By assuming plane strain, the radial strain, ϵ_R , reduces to zero and the web width remains constant. Therefore at a distance y from the neutral axis, equation (1) reduces to:

$$\frac{L_y T_y}{L_0 T_0} = 1 \quad (9)$$

The arc length of a segment at distance y from the neutral axis is:

$$L_y = (R_0 + y) \theta$$

Since $y=0$ at the neutral axis,

$$L_0 = R_0 \theta$$

Substituting into (9), and solving for the thickness ratio yields:

$$\frac{T_0}{T_y} = \frac{(R_0 + y) \theta}{R_0 \theta} = \left(1 + \frac{y}{R_0}\right)$$

Since $y = R_y - R_0$, the thickness ratio in terms of the angular strain, ϵ_θ , becomes:

$$\frac{T_0}{T_y} = (1 + \epsilon_\theta) \quad (10)$$

This equation determines a thickness ratio map for the initial sheet.

Fig. 6 Graph of thickness ratio as a function of angular strain. Number of plies based on final thickness of 2.54 mm (0.100 in) with 0.127 mm (0.005 in) thick plies.

Since this is a radially symmetric problem, the cross section in the transverse direction will remain constant for the entire sheet. For a given radius and distance from the neutral axis, the angular strain at a given location can be calculated:

$$\epsilon_{\theta} = \frac{y}{R_0} \quad (11)$$

From this, the thickness ratio and the required number of plies may be determined.

Fig. 7 Schematic of initial sheet layup for a radius of 254 mm (10 in) and width of 50.8 mm (2 in).

4. Draw Forming (Three Dimensional)

The most realistic and also the most complicated geometry to analyze for thinning is the draw forming of a complex, three dimensional shape. A closed solution could be developed in which the final part is divided into finite segments and then the strain field determined based on the final geometry and the boundary conditions. Complexity of such an analysis would greatly depend on the part geometry. Another technique could use a finite element forming program⁷ that would actually model the forming using experimentally determined material properties. This technique could produce the most detailed solutions, but since each forming step is the same as a full finite element analysis, a complete forming sequence would be expensive and time consuming.

A practical alternative to these techniques is a novel approach recently developed to analyze the thinning in a seat shaped structure. This technique combines an actual model of the molds with a general mathematical analysis. Instead of using a computer to simulate the entire forming process, the mold model determines the geometrical transformation and then a computer is used to convert that to the predicted thickness ratios and finally the required initial sheet contour.

An actual model of the male and female mold halves must be fabricated. The female mold must be made from a transparent material, such as Lucite* acrylic resin. Then a thin rubber sheet is used to model the thermoformable sheet material at the forming temperature. Since rubber has a Poisson's ratio of 0.5, it is an ideal material to model plastic deformation, where a Poisson's ratio of 0.5 can be assumed.⁸ This material is clamped in a frame just as it would be clamped in the actual forming equipment. An orthogonal grid is drawn on the elastic sheet. This sheet is then stretched over the male mold to simulate the actual forming. The transparent, female mold is then used to compress the elastic material. The distorted grid can then be easily seen through the female mold. Detailed measurements of the lengths and diagonals of each segment of this distorted grid are then made to document this geometrical transformation.

These detailed measurements are then entered into a computer for the thickness ratio analysis. First the area of each grid is calculated using the measured lengths and diagonals. Then an average final area is calculated by averaging the areas of the grid segments inside a region. The size of a region is determined by the mean fiber length in the composite material. Then, using conservation of volume:

$$T_0 = \frac{A_1}{A_0} T_1$$

* Du Pont registered trademark

where A_0 is the area of an initial grid segment and A_1 is the area of the final distorted grid. This calculation is repeated for each individual grid over the entire sheet. The result of this is a contour plot of the initial sheet showing the required number of plies at each location.

Fig. 8 Diagram of contoured plies required to form uniform 3.8 mm (0.15 in) thick seat from 0.20 mm (0.008 in) laminates and a photograph of the formed seat.

This technique was successfully used on a half size composite seat. A contoured sheet was made based on the results of the above analysis using a quarter scale model. This ordered staple thermoformable sheet material was made using Du Pont's Kevlar® aramid fiber in a matrix of J2 amorphous nylon thermoplastic resin. The fiber volume fraction in this panel was 75%. The panel was then formed into a half size seat using matched metal tooling. The final part had uniform thickness as predicted by this analysis.

There are several limitations to this technique. First, it depends on how closely the rubber material forms compared to the actual thermoformable sheet. Second, the degree of sticking or slipping of the material over the surface of the mold cannot be duplicated with the model. And finally, an iteration on the contoured ply layout may be needed once the initial parts have been formed and inspected.

CONCLUSIONS

A major concern in forming thermoplastic composite sheet materials is the thinning of the sheet where it is drawn. Several techniques were described to predict this thinning. For simple geometries, an analytical approach is feasible. For more complex geometries, an actual model coupled with a computer analysis can be used to predict thinning. Once the thinning is known, an initial contoured sheet may be designed so that the final formed part is uniformly thick. An example of forming a complex seat part was described.

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